

Scoping considerations
for the request addressed to the European Group on Ethics in
Science and New Technologies (EGE)
to develop an Opinion on
the Value of Nature

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THE VALUE OF NATURE AND VALUING NATURE

It is necessary to go beyond monetisation approaches, while noting that among the manifold reactions to the biodiversity and climate crises are attempts to value nature in economic and monetary terms. The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), for example, highlights that most policymaking approaches have prioritised a narrow set of values at the expense of both nature and society, supporting short-term profit and ‘economic growth’. It found that achieving sustainable and just futures require institutions that enable a recognition and integration of broader understandings of the intrinsic value of nature and its value for human and other forms of life.¹

Questions about the value of nature can be assessed from a variety of viewpoints and deeply relate to questions about the place of humans in nature, as part of nature, and vis-à-vis other parts of nature, as well as to questions about the sustainability of our current economic system (‘green growth’, ‘degrowth’, ‘beyond growth’, “post-growth”).

Relevant conceptual and analytical lenses in this area of discussion may also include anthropocentrism, speciesism, ecocentrism (incl. perspectives from ‘indigenous’ communities); global justice; stewardship, custodianship, ownership; intergenerational and interspecies ethics; relational ethics, care ethics; the role of science, innovation and new technologies.

EU policy background:

As part of the European Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 is the EU’s plan to put biodiversity on the path to recovery by 2030. It contains specific commitments and actions to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems, building on existing European nature laws. The Birds and Habitats Directives (“Nature Directives”) are the

¹ Assessment Report on Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature | UNEP - UN Environment Programme

EU's oldest environmental laws. They form the backbone of EU biodiversity policy and are the legal basis for Natura 2000 – the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world. The Environmental Liability Directive has been providing an EU-wide liability regime for environmental damage. By making those that have caused environmental damage liable for remediation, it provides a strong incentive to avoid damage occurring in the first place. It also makes those whose activities threaten the environment liable for taking preventive action. In the context of the Better Regulation agenda (with its Better Regulation Toolbox), the European Commission aims to ensure that all legislative proposals contribute to the 2030 sustainable development agenda. It requires that impacts in qualitative, quantitative and monetary terms are assessed where possible. The European Green Deal, in addition to previous specifications, centrally builds on sustainable economic growth. As described above, funds that would trigger 'green' growth are core parts of the EU's current environmental and climate policies (as also explained the European Commission's [answer](#) to the [Parliamentary Question E-002894/2023](#). Some of its instruments are based on approaches that attempt to monetarily capture the value of nature, notably the [Emissions Trading System](#), while the Carbon Removal Certification Framework aims at creating transparency, and the [Regulation on land, land use change and forestry](#) establishes targets on carbon removal.

This Opinion should be completed by the end of*(date to be determined)*.

Questions to the EGE:

Which assumptions about the value of nature, biodiversity, ecosystems and of the relationship of humans to nature should underpin policy decisions? How are these dimensions integrated into (economic) policymaking at EU and national levels, and in underlying models used for impact assessment, policy design, monitoring and evaluation? On this basis, what kinds of governance action are required, also with regard to the further development of the European Green Deal and of what is to follow it, and the EU's strategies and actions in the global context?

What are important ethical considerations as regards conceptualisations about the rights and standing of non-human parts of nature? Who is best placed to invoke, enshrine, and adjudicate these rights – and on what basis?

How are approaches that value nature, and human actions with effect on nature, in economic terms to be assessed from an ethical perspective? What are important ethical perspectives as regards socio-economic systems and the need for a global transition to sustainability?

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